

EXPLORERS

Exceed your limits.
Become the BEST.

Sonoma State University
Department of Electrical Engineering

sonoma.edu/engineering

@SSU_Engineering

Sonoma State University is a public university part of the 23-campus California State University (CSU) system. Regularly named a “Best Regional University”, it has also been named one of the “most wired” campuses in the nation.

The **Engineering Department** is distinguished by its state-of-the art laboratories and strong ties to the local high-tech industries. The Department focuses on hands-on and project-based learning and it offers exciting paid research and training opportunities to all engineering students. Many of our alums work for big names, including Keysight, Parker Hannifin, Xilinx, Broadcom, Disney, Fitbit, PG&E, Google, Tesla, and Apple.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x1 CHALLENGE

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Health
Transport
Environment

CHALLENGE #1 - SSU-LORA-01

→ **Transmit one bit the longest using the least power utilizing LoRa**

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Image processing / Cloud computing / smart cities

OBJECTIVES

Develop the building blocks required to evolve towards a smart city

SKILLS REQUIRED

Communications / programming / Python / Hardware

